

Factors of students' non-lecture attendance and administrative strategies for its effective management in Nigerian universities

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to investigate factors of students' non lecture attendance and administrative strategies used with a view to ascertain the extent of its implementation in universities in South-South states in Nigeria. A population of 22 universities from which a sample of six was drawn and 350 respondents; 50 lecturers and 300 students formed the sample size. The study was guided by three research questions and adopted the descriptive survey research design. A questionnaire was the instrument used for the study. It was divided into four subsections, which is part A, B, C and D. Its face and content validity were determined through expert judgment while the reliability index was determined using Cronbach alpha. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data collected. The findings revealed that emotional problems (3.93), sickness (3.71), finance (3.48), lecturers teaching skills (3.21) were key factors of non-lecture attendance. The main administrative strategies used were 75% policy on lecture attendance (3.33), administering short and unannounced quiz (3.24), provision of comfortable classrooms (3.30); while the strategies were sometimes used. The recommendations include counseling students and a 100% implementation of any policy adopted by individual universities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Quality teaching in universities equip students with the requisite skills, knowledge and initiatives, to provide, enhance and sustain enduring socioeconomic wellbeing of nations. It avails learners with the needed skills for good governance and entrepreneurship and also provides avenues for local and global career engagement opportunities. In essence, quality teaching in universities is imperative. Among the many ways of teaching in universities is the lecture method. It is an oral presentation by an instructor to a group of learners. It is regarded as the most suitable method of teaching especially when a large content of learning materials needs to be taught to a large audience. The use of lecture method exposes students to modern, scientific and innovative materials. When used in conjunction with engaging students' participation, it has the potential to improve teaching and learning [1].

Lecture attendance is the physical or virtual presence in a class. It is important because it is critical to academic performance. Research works showed that there is a statistically significant relationship between attendance and performance in tests, examinations and other assessment procedures [2], [3]. Lecture attendance helps students to gain a better understanding of the topic, concepts and principles presented to them. It provides students with the opportunity to share experiences, form effective communication skills with fellow students, promotes class cohesion and positive dynamics among peers. Physical presence at

lectures aids overall study efficiency and reduction in one's own study time and presents opportunity to be coached in answering examination type questions [4], [5]. In spite of these benefits, previous research [6], [7] maintain that lecture attendance is low in tertiary institutions. This could be appreciated given the fact that technology enabled learning devices is becoming common place. Students are able to miss lectures and catch up online, which unfortunately may be insufficient for deep learning required at this level of education. More so, as a result of the high cost of university education many students are no longer able to focus on their degree fulltime because of part time work and other commitments.

Research studies have explored various factors which may influence students' non-attendance to classes. Research by Dolnicar *et al.* [8] categorized the factors as university and student related (including socioeconomic and pedagogical factors). Among the institutional related factors, lecture quality is one of the most significant factors cited. Several researches [9]–[11] reported that a lecturer's knowledge of the subject matter, the inability to present same in a structured manner could influence attendance. Research by Nwamaka *et al.* [12] established that teachers' job negligence influences classroom attendance. In a study by Sloan *et al.* [13], students were asked to compare different teaching sessions by rating their likelihood of attendance on a scale of 1-5, they found that field trips were the most likely session to be attended due to the high level of interactions among the students and the lecturer.

The relevance of a lecture in relation to an assignment or examination could influence attendance. Research by Oldfield *et al.* [9] observed that students were more likely to attend teaching sessions when they perceived that it was either related to examinations or assignments. Another study has shown that poor state of facilities; lack of electricity, inadequate capacity of lecture halls and conveniences are key issues in lecture attendance in some universities in South-South states of Nigeria. Poor state of facilities without electricity, inadequate capacity of lecture halls, and the inability to hear the lecturer are key issues of non-lecture attendance [14]. Similarly, some research findings revealed that class size is another factor in class attendance. When a class is large, it is difficult to spot absentees and some students may feel that their absence may not be recognized and skip lectures. Students see themselves as faces in a sea of faces and lecturers would not notice if they were in class and there would be no repercussions [9].

Lecture attendance may depend on the time and day of the week. Previous research [11], [15] noted that attendance was particularly lower in the afternoons between 15.30-16.30 on Friday. However, Kelly [10] pointed out that there is a negligible difference between attendance in the morning and afternoon lectures and concluded that Mondays were the best and Fridays, the worst days to fix lectures. A study conducted by Swanepoel *et al.* [15] in a South African university in Cape Town on 672 first year micro economics students reported that lecture attendance was lower in the afternoon and on Fridays.

Another factor which could influence attendance is time tabling issues. It accounted for 8% reasons for non-attendance because of the awkwardness of the time being either too early or long gaps between sessions [13]. They recognized that sessions prior to 10am accounted for high level of absenteeism. Research by Kottasz [11] observed that 38% of students missed lectures because they were able to get lecture handout materials from other sources. In contrast, Jordaan [16] argued that despite the availability of online materials, the average class attendance was not affected because students regarded online materials as additional aids in assisting them pass the subject they enrolled for and not something that could replace lecture attendance.

Among student-based factors, motivation has been found to have a huge influence on attendance either intrinsically or extrinsically. Research by Clay and Breslow [17] stated that when students have the privilege of selecting their subjects and seem to be doing well, they are more motivated to attend lectures. Research by Kassarnig *et al.* [18] in a study on class attendance, divided the class into three groups; low achievers, moderate performance grades and high achievers. When the average attendance for each group was computed, it was observed that the rate of absence among the low achievers was consistently higher compared to moderate and high-performance groups. This implies that people who are not motivated are likely to be absent.

Some studies claimed that finance is a very important factor in lecture attendance. According to Nnamani *et al.* [19], poor economic condition could be a source of emotional troubles. It could damage self-esteem and lead to non-attendance at lectures. Furthermore, when students perceive they can get lecture materials from alternative sources, they may not attend lectures.

The influence of peer pressure is another important factor in lecture attendance. Students feel obliged to attend lectures only because friends and peers attended [11]. In the same vein, if students perceived negative undercurrent regarding the lecturer, attendance is affected [18]. Study by Sloan *et al.* [13] discovered that illness, laziness, failure to get up on time, socializing and having to work late night shifts determines the choice to attend lectures. Research by Muir [20] raised the fact that sickness was the most common factor followed by assignments and the feeling that it would be a waste of time. Students' inability to prioritize time effectively leads to absenteeism [21].

Non-attendance at lectures produces negative effects on both the students, institutions and the society. Several studies [2], [22]–[24] lamented that students who do not attend lectures do not get properly socialized in professional behaviors and habits expected of them after graduation. Poor lecture attendance

could tell negatively on the reputation of the institution and might even affect enrolment into such institution as parents may be unwilling to patronize schools with low morale and reputation. In the same context, Ezeji [25] noted that non-attendance at lectures has led to students' involvement in dangerous crimes that are prevalent in higher institutions such as, drug intake and abuse, sexual harassment, rape, examination malpractice, sex in exchange for marks, unmerited upgrade of scores among others. These crimes have impacted fear, trauma, depression and aggressive behaviors on their victims [7]. Non-attendance could result in poor grades, wastage of government investment in education and eventual dropping out of school.

Research studies have suggested measures employed by tertiary institutions to curb non-attendance at lectures in tertiary institutions. Research by Muir [20] on students' absenteeism reported that in a population of 44, 41% advocated that a register of attendance be taken and penalties served to those who did not attend and rewards to those who did. It further suggested that those who failed a course with low attendance should be required to retake the course with attendance the following year. Previous research [11], [15] recommended the use of orientation programmed to fully acquaint new students who may not have made the shift from high school to university schedule of programmed where the work load is heavier. Some research works support the adoption of the 75% attendance policy rule which states that eligibility for any course for which a student has been fully registered must have attained a minimum of 75% contact hours [26]–[28]. Furthermore, Karnik *et al.* [6] observed that the use of the 75% policy rule on attendance could send a message to potential employers on the high priority an institution places on instruction and learning outcomes. As another management strategy, classes should be made more interesting with practical real-life examples, take- in assignment, unannounced tests, and bonus marks for attendees [17], [29]. Fröberg and Jonsson [22] pointed out four options; that students should be allowed to express themselves without limitations, lecturers should use different teaching methods and make materials relevant in relation to course outline and the need for lecturers to be more engaged enthusiastically in presenting the subject matter.

Given that attendance is low in Fridays late afternoons, Swanepoel *et al.* [15] suggested an urgent need to adjust the time table to either exclude certain slots or spend specific days (Mondays to Wednesdays) for first year students to save students transportation time. Other strategies include the use of technologies, counseling students; informing parents, use of reward and punishment, providing comfortable lecture halls [30]. Additionally, Olufunmilayo [27] emphasized that lecture rooms should be more spacious, with adequate ventilation and comfortable seats for learning. Jacksi *et al.* [31] suggested the use of electronic student's attendance management system against manual system as the later is time consuming, a source of distraction, subject to mutilation and impersonation especially in a large class. These aforementioned strategies could be meaningful when effectively applied [32], [33]. Negative administrative attitude forestalls implementation of administrative policies [34]. It is in line with the foregoing that this study explores the key factors that hinder students' lecture attendance and the various administrative strategies employed in the sampled universities with a view to ascertain the extent of implementation of identified strategies.

Regular attendance at lectures helps students to gain a better understanding of the topic, provides students with the opportunities to form effective communication skills with fellow students and improve overall study efficiency and reduction in one's own study time. The massive use of e learning during COVID-19 opened up new ways of online independent study which has exacerbated the non-attendance issue. The cost of university education has also increased and students have to work at the expense of lecture attendance. To further complicate the situation, Government grants, scholarships and allowances are no longer available. The researchers have observed that some students are not regular at lectures in spite of the various administrative strategies adopted by universities to curb this development. It is against this backdrop that the study was carried out to unravel the key factors responsible for students non lecture attendance, the administrative strategies employed as well as the extent to which the strategies are implemented. Thus, the research questions of the study were formulated as:

- i) What are the key factors of students' non lecture attendance in universities in South-South Nigeria?
- ii) What are the administrative strategies employed for the management of students' non lecture attendance in universities in South-South Nigeria?
- iii) What is the extent of application of the identified administrative strategies in dealing with students' non lecture attendance in universities in South-South Nigeria?

2. METHOD

The researchers used descriptive survey design and employed the ex-post facto method because it blends qualitative and quantitative data to provide relevant and accurate information on students' non lecture attendance. The population for the study was all the 22 public universities in six states that make up the South-South states in Nigeria: Edo (3), Delta (7), Rivers (3), Bayelsa (4), Akwa Ibom (3), and Cross River (2). The random sampling technique was used to select six universities from which a sample of 300 students and 50

lecturers were randomly selected from the population. The researchers' designed questionnaire titled, "factors of students' non lecture attendance and administrative strategies questionnaire" (FOSNLAASQ) was the instrument used for data collection. It has four sub sections: part A entailed the demographic information of the respondents; part B, 20 items of factors of students' non lecture attendance (FOSNLA) while part C entailed 12 items on administrative strategies for its effective management (ASEM). Parts B and C were structured on a 4-point Likert scale of strongly agree (SA)=4 points, agree (A)=3, disagree (SD)=2 and strongly disagree (D)=1.

Part D of the instrument contained 12 factors on the extent of application of the identified administrative strategies (EAIS) and was structured on a three-point scale of always (3 points), sometimes (2 points) and never (1 point). The face and content validity were determined by two experts in the Department of Educational Management and Foundations who read through the initial draft and their contributions were incorporated into producing the final manuscript of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was determined by administering it to 20 persons outside the study group. The Cronbach alpha reliability computation of the three sub sections were; 0.75, 0.78 and 0.76 for part B (FOSNLA), parts C (ASEM) and D (EAIS) respectively. This was an indication that the instrument's internal consistency was adequate for use. The researcher employed two research assistants in the administration of the instrument at each institution. A total of 350 copies of the questionnaire were administered in six universities. The 350 copies were returned valid and used for the study. The data was analyzed with the use of mean score and standard deviation. The benchmark of 2.50 was used for acceptance of an item while scores below 2.50 were not accepted in sections B (FOSNLA) and C (ASEM). While in section D (EAIS), the benchmark for acceptance was 1.50 and items below 1.50 were not accepted.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Research question 1

Table 1 shows the factors of students' non lecture attendance, mean score, standard deviation and remarks. The table shows that all the responses from item 1-18 were agreed on with a mean range of 2.58-3.93 and a grand mean of 2.96 which was above the benchmark of 2.50 as the factors affecting students non lecture attendance in tertiary institutions in South-South, Nigeria.

3.2. Research question 2

Table 2 shows the administrative strategies employed in the management of students' non lecture attendance, mean, standard deviation and remarks. The table shows that respondents agreed to items 1-12 with a mean range of 2.65-3.30 and a grand mean of 2.92 which were above the cut off mark of 2.50 as management strategies adopted for students non lecture attendance in tertiary institutions in South-South, Nigeria.

3.3. Research question 3

Table 3 shows the extent of the administrative strategies employed, the mean scores, standard deviation and remarks. The table indicates that the respondents agreed to items 1-12 with a mean range of 1.94-2.60 and a grand mean range of 2.14 that sometimes they apply management options on students non lecture attendance in tertiary institutions in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 1. Mean and standard deviation on factors of students non lecture attendance (N=300)

S/N	Factors in students non lecture attendance	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Lecturers teaching skills	3.21	0.96	Agree
2	Unfriendly attitudes of lecturers	2.58	0.07	Agree
3	Inconvenient lecture time	3.26	0.77	Agree
4	Socializing activities – parties, meetings	3.14	0.82	Agree
5	Lack of parental support	2.79	0.45	Agree
6	Alternative source of lecture materials determines my attendance	2.87	0.93	Agree
7	Friends determine my attendance	2.94	0.78	Agree
8	Work commitment determines my attendance	2.98	0.81	Agree
9	Unconducive lecture halls	3.35	0.48	Agree
10	Distance from hall of residence	2.76	0.48	Agree
11	Sickness	3.71	0.71	Agree
12	Day of the week determines my attendance	2.74	0.63	Agree
13	Financial issues	3.48	0.50	Agree
14	Laziness	2.93	0.69	Agree
15	Past poor performance	3.21	0.41	Agree
16	Difficult course	2.68	0.38	Agree
17	Emotional problems	3.93	0.38	Agree
18	Depending on examination malpractice	2.80	0.36	Agree
19	Transportation issues	1.81	0.33	Disagree
20	Completing assignment at the last minute	1.94	0.99	Disagree
	Total grand mean	2.96	0.61	

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation on administrative strategies adopted (N=50)

S/N	Management strategies adopted	Mean	SD	Remark
1	The use of technological devices to take attendance	2.74	0.90	Agree
2	Use of different teaching methods	2.84	0.04	Agree
3	A continuous analysis of individual student's attendance	2.65	0.61	Agree
4	The use of counseling techniques	2.96	0.60	Agree
5	Establish awards for lecturers to enhance professionalism in teaching	2.74	0.23	Agree
6	Seek parents support	2.60	0.53	Agree
7	Give short and unannounced quiz	3.24	0.80	Agree
8	Provide comfortable classrooms	3.30	0.74	Agree
9	Orientation of new students	3.28	0.90	Agree
10	Application of 75% policy attendance	3.34	0.80	Agree
11	Award of marks for attendance	3.28	0.76	Agree
12	Make teaching materials relevant to course outline	2.70	0.46	Agree
	Total grand mean	2.92	0.61	Agree

Table 3. Mean and standard deviation on the extent of utilization of management strategies (N=50)

S/N	Extent of application	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Technological devices are used to take class attendance	1.98	0.74	Sometimes
2	The 75% policy is used in my institution	2.24	0.80	Sometimes
3	My institution uses counseling techniques	1.94	0.87	Sometimes
4	My institution organizes orientation for new students	2.60	0.59	Sometimes
5	Awards are given to lecturers for quality teaching	2.12	0.67	Sometimes
6	In my institution, parents support is sought	2.16	0.84	Sometimes
7	In my institution, lecturers give unannounced quiz	2.08	0.90	Sometimes
8	My institution provides comfortable classrooms	1.98	0.80	Sometimes
9	Lecturers make teaching materials relevant to course outline	2.04	0.86	Sometimes
10	Posters and leaflets are used to promote attendance	2.14	0.81	Sometimes
11	My institution awards marks for attendance	2.30	0.74	Sometimes
12	A critical follow up on causative factors are observed in my institution	2.04	0.86	Sometimes
	Total grand mean	2.14	0.79	

3.4. Discussion

The finding showed that the respondents agreed to items 1-18 as the factors of students' non lecture attendance in universities in South-South Nigeria. The key factors identified in this study were emotional problems (3.93), sickness (3.71), finance (3.48), lecturers teaching skills (3.21), inconvenient lecture time (3.26), unconducive lecture halls (3.35) and socializing (3.14). This shows that personal factors are most critical to students' lecture attendance. When a student is faced with personal challenges, the zeal to attend lectures will be lacking. This finding corroborated the studies [13], [30] who pointed out that the main factors of students non lecture attendance were, health, institutional, poverty and peer related factors. In addition, Muir [20] found that sickness was a major factor in non-lecture attendance. In contrast to this finding, in a study on reasons for non-lecture attendance in a South African University, emphasized the key factors to include time table clashes, studying for another subject, traffic and transportation problems and oversleeping [29]. In the same vein, a study [15] investigated non-attendance of third year commerce students in Wollongong University concluded that students' motivation and attitude towards learning came to the fore as major reasons for non-lecture attendance. This finding goes to buttress the universality of non-lecture attendance with a variation of factors according to countries and their economic status.

The second finding of the study showed that all the options for administrative strategies were agreed upon; especially application of 75% policy on attendance (3.34), provision of comfortable classrooms (3.30), orientation of new students (3.28), award of marks for attendance (3.28) and giving short and unannounced quiz (3.24). These administrative strategies employed by universities would promote discipline, responsibility and commitment to studies. More so, these measures would ensure improved study habits and greater participation in class. This view corroborated [13], [26], [27] whose studies indicated that making test and quizzes count as part of students' continuous assessment encouraged attendance; that 75% lecture attendance policy would improve the overall performance of students and guarantee their satisfactory results; and that classrooms should be well ventilated, spacious enough to conveniently accommodate the total number of students per lecture. Research by Kassarnig *et al.* [18] also noted that adopting the policy would encourage attendance and send a positive image of the institution to potential employees. On the issue of orientation, this finding also aligned with Swanepoel *et al.* [15] that new students should be properly integrated into tertiary education systems because some of them may not have successfully made the transition from high school to university programmed where the work load is heavier.

The findings established that administrative management options were sometimes applied in the management of students' non-attendance at lectures. When policies are sometimes applied, it gives room for

students to flaunt university policies. The findings revealed that a gap exists between the implementation stage and attainment of desired goals. This could be attributed to negative attitude of management staff at the implementation stage and this explains why students' non-attendance at lectures persists. Lending credence to this, several research [32], [33] affirmed that ineffective implementation of educational policies in Nigerian universities is attributed to lack of good governance/continuity, accountability, and corruption. This has led to the inability of university management to meet educational standard and goals in the 21st century. Furthermore, educational policies fail when there is little appreciation of the fact that building support for policies is an integral part of designing them [34].

The findings of this study have far-reaching implications for planning and administration of university education. This is because non lecture attendance could result in poor academic performance, getting involved in anti-social behaviors, dropout and wastage of educational resources. On the part of the institution, it could portray a negative image of unserious academic pursuit on the part of university administrators and this could lead to low patronage.

4. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the key factors of students' non lecture attendance in universities in the South-South states of Nigeria were emotional problems, sickness, finance, lecturers' teaching skills, inconvenient timetable, unconducive lecture halls, and socializing. The administrative strategies adopted by management were 75% attendance policy, provision of comfortable lecture halls, award of marks for attendance, administering short unannounced quiz and making it count as part of students' continuous assessment. The study further concludes that although universities in the South-South states applied some administrative strategies in the management of lecture attendance, the identified strategies were sometimes implemented and this explained why the problem persists. The recommendations were: i) university authorities should provide guidance and counseling units where students can get effective and adequate counseling while in school; ii) university management should provide sufficiently equipped health centers with adequate personnel to provide health care facilities to sick students; iii) the government, private companies, religious bodies and philanthropic organizations should introduce scholarship schemes to reduce the burden on students with financial issues to enable them attend lectures; iv) management of universities should give awards to lecturers for best teaching practices and organize workshops and symposia to help improve lecturers' teaching skills to enhance attendance at lectures; v) the government and management of universities should provide comfortable lecture halls with adequate ventilation, furniture, electricity and conveniences to aid improvement at lecture attendance; and vi) there should be one hundred percent implementation of any policy adopted by university management and defaulters should be penalized.

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